

FAIR Data

In 2016, Mark D. Wilkinson et al. published the *FAIR Guiding Principles for Scientific Data Management and Stewardship* to optimize the publication and reusability of research data. FAIR is an acronym for **F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable and **R**eusable and consists of a set of [15 principles](#).

The Swiss National Science Foundation and other research funders require data to be published in a FAIR way. In order to comply with the (complex) FAIR principles, we offer the following recommendations:

Findable	Accessible
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Add metadata to your data, so that the data can be found.• Add a persistent identifier (e.g. a DOI) to be able to reference data unambiguously.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Publish the data online in a repository for re-search data.• If data publication is not possible (e.g. due to legal restrictions), publish metadata online and clearly state the restrictions for accessibility.
Interoperable	Reusable
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Use metadata standards and standardized controlled vocabularies to describe your data.• Use file formats recommended for data archiving, as these are generally widespread and readable by many software programs and can still be read in the long term.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Provide sufficient documentation on your data, e.g. on the context of origin and all data processing.• Add a license that is as open as possible to make it clear how the data may be reused. In the context of research data, CC licenses are widely used; CC0 or CC-BY are particularly recommended.

Check it out: Use a [self-assessment checklist](#) to improve the FAIRness of your dataset.

